

DEVELOPMENT OF A REFLECTANCE PULSE OXIMETER FOR PATIENT SELF-MONITORING

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Abstract— Pulse oximetry is a non-invasive method that allows the measurement and monitoring of blood oxygenation and heart rate. This method utilizes the differential absorption of light by oxygenated and deoxygenated hemoglobin to construct a calibration curve and estimate the percentage of oxygen saturation in the bloodstream. This article details the complete development of a portable pulse oximetry device that estimates blood oxygenation using the principle of light absorption via the reflectance method. The project encompasses the design and implementation of its electronic hardware, the physical enclosure, and an accompanying mobile application.

Keywords — Oximetry, Reflectance, Pulse Oximetry, Hemoglobin, Oxygen Saturation Monitoring.

I. INTRODUCTION

Pulse oximetry enables the non-invasive measurement of blood oxygen levels. As it does not require a blood sample, this method facilitates the development of portable devices for continuous and accurate monitoring [1].

The constant monitoring of blood oxygen levels is crucial to detect and monitor respiratory diseases that can affect oxygen saturation. In severe cases, continuous oxygen monitoring of intubated patients is essential to control and stabilize the patient's condition [2].

The importance of monitoring oxygen levels became more evident during the COVID-19 pandemic, as the disease significantly impacted respiratory functions [3]. Consequently, various measures were required to monitor numerous patients, including remote monitoring. This enabled patients to undergo monitoring from their homes, providing healthcare professionals with remote access to their oxygen saturation levels and facilitating rapid intervention if oxygen levels were low [4].

In this context, the development and improvement of portable medical devices have become increasingly necessary [5]. Among these, the non-invasive nature of oxygen measurement devices is attributable to the relationship between light absorption by oxygenated

hemoglobin (oxyhemoglobin) and deoxygenated hemoglobin (deoxyhemoglobin). Oxygen levels subtly alter the blood's color, enabling the differentiation of saturation levels [6].

To estimate blood oxygen saturation, a calibration curve is essential. This curve is typically established by correlating known oxygen levels in a sample with corresponding light absorption measurements. This estimation can be performed using the Beer-Lambert law (Eq. 1), which relates light absorption to the concentration of the sample [7].

$$A = \varepsilon \cdot c \cdot l \quad (1)$$

Where:

- A Absorbance, the amount of light absorbed by a solution.
- ε Molar extinction coefficient of the substance.
- c Concentration of the substance in solution.
- l Optical path length through the solution.

A pulse oximeter fundamentally consists of two light-emitting diodes (LEDs), that emit a different wavelength, and operate in conjunction with a photodiode that serves as a light receiver. When LEDs emit light, it will reach the body tissue and penetrate, part of the light will be reflected by the human body tissues, and this reflected light will be detected by the photodiode, making it possible to calculate the absorption by the tissues and blood composition. Using the calibration curve and the Beer-Lambert law allows us to estimate the levels of blood oxygen saturation [8].

This article discusses the development of a portable pulse oximeter for continuous oxygenation monitoring, covering its hardware design, mechanical parts, firmware, and software. Additionally, an Android application was developed to track blood oxygen levels.

II. METHODOLOGY

The development of this pulse oximeter prototype involved a series of interdependent steps and the seamless integration of all hardware and software components. The complete operating logic and structural integration of its

components, which collectively ensure the proper functioning of the oximeter, are depicted in the block diagram detailed in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Block diagram representing the structure and integration of the systems comprising the oximeter.

As seen in the previous diagram (Figure 1), the project consists of components that integrate with each other to ensure the correct operation of the circuit. The following topics will describe the stages of the project development.

A. Hardware

A.a Power Supply

The power supply is a critical component in the development of any electronic circuit, particularly those designed for portable use requiring battery operation and low power consumption. It can directly influence the accuracy and safety of the device. To ensure safe and efficient operation, the developed circuit was designed to be powered by two 3V batteries, yielding a total of 6V. The battery-powered design was also chosen to minimize noise and harmonics typically associated with mains power supply, offering enhanced protection by avoiding direct contact with the electrical grid.

To perform the voltage regulation, the LM7805 voltage regulator was utilized to reduce the battery voltage to a stable 5V. This component is essential for the circuit to have a stable voltage. Subsequently, this 5V was further regulated down to 3.3V by the internal voltage regulator of the ESP32 microcontroller. From this point onwards, the ESP32 microcontroller powers the entire circuitry of the device, ensuring all components receive the appropriate voltage for their operation. Figure 2 illustrates the schematic of the power supply control circuit, where P1 represents the battery connector.

Fig. 2. Power supply control circuit.

A.b Reference Circuit

For accurate oxygenation measurements, the stability of circuit components is paramount, ensuring their electrical properties remain constant throughout operation. A reliable reference voltage (REF) is required, as any fluctuation or instability can result in errors, which compromise the reliability of the device. To achieve the desired reference voltage, a resistive voltage divider was implemented. This divider was connected to the microcontroller's 3.3V output and specifically designed to provide a stable reference voltage of 1.65V. The resistors chosen for this divider were R13 and R14, as shown in Figure 5, which are both 10k Ω . This configuration ensures that the reference point for analog-to-digital conversion remains stable.

A.c Emitting Circuit

The current driver is responsible for providing a stable current to the LEDs. It is crucial to ensure that the emitted light also remains constant. The constancy is crucial for the accuracy of the measurements.

For the emitting circuit, two light-emitting diodes (LEDs) were utilized, emitting at wavelengths of 660 nm (Red) and 940 nm (Infrared), respectively. To switch and control the intensity of the LEDs, a constant current source was employed for each, leveraging the principle that an LED's light emission is directly proportional to the current flowing through it. Specifically, NPN transistors (BC547BTF, Q1 and Q2, as shown in Figure 3) were used in a common-emitter configuration to act as current sources for each LED.

The current values for each LED were precisely defined using series resistors R8 (1.5 k Ω) and R10 (1.8 k Ω) for the Red and Infrared LEDs, respectively, as depicted in Figure 3. This approach was taken to ensure that the photodiode's sensitivity response was adequately matched for both wavelengths, compensating for its inherent spectral responsivity variations. This calibration is necessary because the photodiode sensitivity varies depending on the wavelength. This circuit is illustrated in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Emitting circuit.

A.d Receiving Circuit

The photodiode (BPW34, U3 in Figure 4) requires proper biasing to operate effectively within the linear region of its characteristic curve. This allows the photodiode to convert the received light intensity into a proportional electrical current. Following the photodiode's current generation, this analog current signal is directed to the MCP6024-E operational amplifier (U1.1 in Figure 4), configured as a transimpedance amplifier. This stage is crucial as it converts the low-level current output from the photodiode into a measurable voltage signal, suitable for subsequent processing by the microcontroller.

Fig. 4. Receptor circuit.

A.e Passive Low-Pass Filter (DC Signal Conditioning)

At the output of the transimpedance amplifier, the DC and AC signal conditioning paths were separated. This separation is critical to prevent the DC component from saturating the AC amplification stage and to enable accurate oxygen saturation calculation in the software. For conditioning the DC signal, a passive low-pass filter was designed with a cutoff frequency of 0.5 Hz. This cutoff was chosen because the majority of the heart rate signal's power spectrum, which typically ranges from 0.8 to 2.5 Hz (corresponding to 50-150 BPM), is contained below 5 Hz, thus effectively isolating the DC component while preserving relevant information. This filter is passive, as it does not require an external power source to operate. Furthermore, it isolates the DC signal, eliminating the AC signal. The circuit for this filter is shown in Figure 5.

A.f Active High-Pass Filter (AC Signal Conditioning)

For conditioning the AC signal, which represents the pulsatile component of blood flow during systole and diastole, an active high-pass filter was employed. This filter allows frequencies above a specific cutoff to pass while blocking or attenuating lower frequencies, including the DC component of the signal. Thus, the cut-off frequency was set at 0.5 Hz to eliminate only the DC signal before it is amplified, preventing the signal from saturating.

An active non-inverting amplifier circuit, utilizing the MCP6024-E operational amplifier (U1.2 in Figure 5), was implemented to provide a gain of 150 to the AC signal. The gain was calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Gain} = 1 + \left(\frac{R_2}{R_1} \right) \quad (2)$$

Where:

Gain	The amplification factor of the circuit.
R_2	The resistance of resistor 2.
R_1	The resistance of resistor 1.

A.g Active Low-Pass Filter

Following the removal of the DC level and the application of the necessary gain, the AC signal undergoes further filtering to isolate the relevant spectral components. This step is essential to eliminate unwanted signals, specifically electromagnetic interference around 60 Hz and other high-frequency noise. Consequently, an active low-pass filter with a cutoff frequency of 17 Hz was implemented (see Figure 5). This cutoff frequency was chosen to capture the physiological pulse signal while effectively suppressing higher frequency noise, including 60 Hz interference.

Fig. 5. Signal Conditioning and Gain Filter Circuit.

B. Software

To ensure intuitive data visualization for the user, a dedicated application for Android devices was developed. Its primary functionality centers on a main screen, where key physiological information, such as oxygenation (SpO_2) and heart rate (BPM), is displayed. The main screen also features a graph that displays the history of the last 20 measurements

taken, allowing them to be tracked over time and enabling subsequent analyses related to health. Additionally, the application includes a robust login and registration system. This feature allows individual users to register and log in, thereby enabling the retention of their personal measurement history and ensuring data privacy and access only by the user who performed the measurement.

The application was developed for Android devices version 13.0 or higher, covering most current smartphones. The application was developed using the Android Studio IDE, Google's official integrated development environment. The backend (functional logic) was implemented in Kotlin, while the frontend (user interface) was designed using XML. Both have full support from Google and extensive documentation.

To establish seamless communication with the hardware device, Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) connection protocols were utilized. This ensures the oximeter remains persistently paired with the Android device, eliminating the need for repeated connection establishments during application use and enabling background operation. Thus, Bluetooth access and control permissions were requested from the user as soon as the application was accessed. With the connection established, the user can choose to take measurements at defined intervals or perform instant measurements.

Upon receiving measurement data, it is then transmitted to a cloud database. This transmission leverages the Android device's internet access, either through a Wi-Fi connection or mobile data provided by a cellular operator. For development and testing purposes of this transmission mechanism, a local web server was developed utilizing the XAMPP tool. XAMPP locally creates a MySQL database, which was used to temporarily store the collected data. Data storage is managed by a Python script that establishes a secure connection with the database and facilitates data transfer for storage via RESTful APIs. RESTful APIs are a set of architectural rules and standards for building web services, enabling efficient communication between disparate software systems. For instance, a specific URL, such as <https://oximed.com/login>, is utilized for user authentication. The Android application sends the username and password, typically in JSON format, to this URL. The Python server-side script then receives this data and performs a verification against the database to confirm if the credentials correspond to an existing user and are correct. If they exist and are correct, the Python server code will return a message to the application, allowing the user to access the measurement screen.

C. Firmware

Firmware development was executed using an Espressif IoT Development Framework (ESP-IDF) based on C/C++ language. The primary focus was on precise photodiode data acquisition, local signal processing, calibration routines, and the efficient transmission of results via Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE). The development stages and the main functionalities implemented are detailed below.

The ESP32 microcontroller's clock frequency was configured to 80 MHz, balancing energy consumption with

performance requirements. System initialization involves two key configurations: first, setting up the Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) communication module to enable direct, real-time data transmission to mobile devices; second, configuring the specific Analog-to-Digital Converter (ADC) pins responsible for reading the oximetry signals. These signals are hardware-separated into AC and DC components for both the infrared (IR) and red (RED) light measurements.

To ensure precise and consistent data collection, a hardware timer was implemented to generate interrupts every 8 ms. This corresponds to a sampling rate of 125 Hz for each LED (Red and IR), which is sufficient to satisfactorily sample the arterial pulsatile signal, considering that a normal human heart rate varies from 0.8 to 1.5 beats per second (50-90 BPM)

During each timer-generated interrupt, the firmware alternates between activating the infrared and red LEDs to collect both AC and DC signal components from the photodiode. To smooth the raw signal and reduce noise, a moving average filter is applied every 10 data points. This filtered data is then collected over a 10-second period, accumulating 1250 samples (125 samples/second * 10 seconds) for each LED, which are subsequently used for the calculation of BPM and SpO₂.

A crucial step for ensuring the reliability of the readings is the verification of the collected signal's stability, which is validated through the calculation of its standard deviation. The system initiates the primary data collection for analysis only after confirming that the signal variation has stabilized and remained within a predefined threshold over a period of 10 consecutive readings. This ensures the measurement is performed on a stable baseline. Following data stabilization and the completion of the 10-second sample window collection, a sophisticated peak and valley analysis algorithm is performed. This algorithm is essential for accurately calculating both heart rate (BPM) and oxygen saturation (SpO₂). A sliding window method is employed to scan the data set, identifying local maximum (peaks) and minimum (valleys) points. The algorithm utilizes a window size of 15 samples for peak/valley detection and enforces a minimum distance of 50 samples between consecutive peaks and valleys to avoid spurious detections. The time interval between one peak and its corresponding subsequent valley is then used to calculate BPM, leveraging the known data sampling frequency (f_s), according to Equation 3:

$$\text{BPM} = \frac{60 \cdot f_s}{N} \quad (3)$$

Where:

BPM	Beats per minute, the heart rate measurement.
f_s	Sampling frequency of the data.
N	Number of samples between a peak and a valley.

After the calculation of BPM from the collected data set, the Ratio (R) value is calculated. This ratio is defined as the quotient of the normalized AC component of the infrared signal by its DC component, divided by the normalized AC component of the red signal by its DC component, as

expressed in Equation 4:

$$\text{ratio} = \frac{\left(\frac{AC_{IR}}{DC_{IR}}\right)}{\left(\frac{AC_{RED}}{DC_{RED}}\right)} \quad (4)$$

Where:

- AC_{IR} AC component of the infrared signal.
- DC_{IR} DC component of the infrared signal.
- AC_{RED} AC component of the red signal.
- DC_{RED} DC component of the red signal.

The SpO_2 value is then derived using an empirically determined calibration coefficient, as shown in Equation 5. This specific coefficient was derived through experimental measurements with a known reference oximeter or blood gas analyzer on a diverse set of samples/volunteers.

$$SpO_2 = 2497.06 \times \text{Ratio} - 2397.84 \quad (5)$$

Where:

- SpO_2 Oxygen saturation level.
- Ratio Values of the red and infrared signals.

The processing of signals and subsequent data notification are performed asynchronously within a dedicated FreeRTOS task, named `processDataTask()`, implemented in the firmware. This task continuously evaluates the system's state and, once data is validated, dispatches the results via BLE to the mobile application. Transmission is initiated only when the collected data is stable and the analysis is complete, avoiding the transmission of erroneous information to the end user.

D. PCB Development

After the successful validation of the circuit schematic through rigorous bench tests, the Printed Circuit Board (PCB) layout was developed using EasyEDA software. The PCB has dimensions of 5x5 cm and consists of two copper layers. The top layer was predominantly covered with a solid ground plane (ground mesh), which helps in reducing electromagnetic interference and improving signal integrity. During the PCB design process, meticulous attention was paid to several critical layout considerations: precise trace sizing and spacing to minimize signal degradation and cross-talk; optimized pad sizes for both small and larger components to ensure reliable soldering; adequate copper clearance around pads; provision of mounting holes for secure board fixation within the enclosure; and a preference for routing critical traces on the bottom layer, especially under larger components, to enhance signal integrity and minimize noise coupling.

Fig. 6. PCB Layout developed using EasyEDA software.

E. 3D Modeling

With the objective of providing mechanical protection for the circuit, enhancing measurement precision, and improving the overall aesthetics of the device, a custom enclosure structure was designed using Fusion360 software. This design aimed to precisely accommodate the PCB and its associated components. Thus, a two-part case was developed: a probe module where the patient comfortably places their finger for measurement, and a main compartment designed to securely house the printed circuit board. The exploded view of this 3D modeled case is presented in Figure 7.

Fig. 7. Exploded view of the 3D-modeled enclosure case.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The development of the pulse oximeter prototype based on the reflectance method reinforced the potential of accessible, low-cost technologies for continuous health monitoring. Throughout the integration process, several practical challenges were addressed, particularly those involving power management and wireless communication.

Initially, the device was designed to operate with two 3V batteries. However, during testing, it became clear

that this configuration did not provide sufficient energy to support all system functionalities—especially during periods of higher current draw, such as during BLE transmission and LED operation. The inclusion of a third battery proved to be a simple yet effective solution, improving stability and ensuring uninterrupted operation, which is essential in real-time monitoring applications.

Data transmission was also a central aspect of the system's performance. By adopting Bluetooth Low Energy and structuring the data into optimized packets, it was possible to ensure fast and consistent communication between the hardware and the mobile application. This design not only minimized latency but also enhanced the reliability of measurements transmitted to the cloud, supporting a potential for real-time remote access.

On the user side, the mobile application played a crucial role in delivering an intuitive experience. Features such as individual login and historical data visualization were implemented with simplicity and privacy in mind, making the system more approachable for end-users without compromising data security.

Even with these advances, the current version of the prototype still presents some limitations. Calibration procedures, for instance, were based on experimental approximations and should be reviewed in future iterations with reference-grade equipment under approved clinical conditions. Additionally, while the energy demand was addressed, further optimization is needed for long-term use and miniaturization. The physical enclosure, although functional, could also benefit from ergonomic improvements to better suit daily or wearable use.

Regarding validation, the implemented tools were verified through functional testing. The hardware prototype was evaluated in bench conditions to confirm the correct operation of the LEDs, photodiode response, and signal acquisition, ensuring that physiological waveforms could be detected and processed. The mobile application was tested for connectivity, verifying that data packets transmitted via BLE were consistently received and stored without interruption. These preliminary validation steps demonstrated the feasibility of the proposed system and its potential for continuous monitoring. Nevertheless, no clinical validation has yet been performed, and future studies must include comparisons with reference-grade devices under standardized protocols to ensure accuracy and reliability in healthcare applications.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study described the design and implementation of a portable reflectance-based pulse oximeter capable of measuring SpO₂ and BPM, integrating both hardware and software components in a compact solution. The combination of analog signal acquisition, microcontroller-based processing, and BLE communication resulted in a functional system with reliable performance under practical conditions.

The use of Bluetooth Low Energy enabled efficient data exchange with a dedicated Android application, which

provided a straightforward interface for users to monitor and track their health metrics. Together with cloud integration, the device demonstrated potential for use in remote or continuous health monitoring scenarios.

Nonetheless, some aspects of the project still require refinement. Calibration accuracy, energy efficiency, and mechanical design remain open points for future development. As next steps, efforts will focus on reducing the device's size, extending battery life, and conducting formal clinical validation. These improvements will be crucial for advancing the prototype toward real-world healthcare applications and increasing its usability in daily routines.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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